

The Economic Experts Survey*

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Abstract

The Economic Experts Survey (EES) is the most comprehensive global survey of economic experts. Established at the ifo Institute in 2022 as the successor to the World Economic Survey (WES), its aim is to capture experts' assessments of economic policy and political developments in their home countries, as well as their views on topical issues in the economic policy debate. Each quarter, the EES surveys around 10,000 experts across over 120 countries, providing real-time insights into experts' perspectives on current economic policy. In this paper, we present an overview of the EES. We describe the survey's coverage and characteristics of its participants, outline the methodological approach and questionnaire design, and briefly describe research based on EES data. We also explain the opportunities for accessing the EES data.

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1 Introduction

Timely and comparable assessments of economic policy and political developments are scarce. Official statistics and household or business surveys are informative but often lag behind the policy cycle or lack cross-country harmonization, Households' and firms' perceptions might also be weakly informed about institutional details. A complementary approach includes economic experts, who offer a critical assessment of economic policy and the political situation in their country based on economic expertise and institutional knowledge. This enables, if measured in a structured manner, the comparison of economic policy assessments across countries in real time.

This paper introduces the Economic Experts Survey (EES), a quarterly global survey of economic experts established at the ifo Institute in 2022 as a successor to the World Economic Survey (WES) (Boumans and Garnitz, 2019). The EES systematically elicits expert assessments of their countries' economic policy and political situation, alongside rotating special modules on topical issues. In each wave, around 10,000 experts worldwide are invited and roughly 1,500 participate, yielding a coverage of over 120 countries and all world regions. Together, these features make the EES the most comprehensive recurring source on expert assessments of economic policy and political stability at the global level.

The EES fills several gaps in the current data landscape. First, it provides quarterly, internationally harmonized measures of expert assessments, overcoming cross-country comparability issues that arise when pooling national surveys. Second, the panel structure supports country- and expert-level longitudinal analysis, allowing researchers to study persistence and changes over time while minimizing compositional effects in the expert sample. Third, the survey augments quantitative ratings with open-ended text responses to capture rationales behind experts' assessments. This can serve as a tool for directed policy advice. Finally, the rotating special modules allow to measure expert views on salient topics using consistent questions across countries.

The purpose of this paper is to provide an overview of the EES for interested researchers. Section 2 describes the EES, including recruitment of experts, geographic coverage and expert characteristics, and core questions. Section 3 summarizes research and policy applications using the EES (and its predecessor), illustrating the types of questions which can be addressed with the dataset. Section 4 explains data access via the LMU-ifo Economics & Business Data Center and outlines documentation, formats, and conditions for academic use.

2 Economic Experts Survey

This section describes the main features of the EES, including expert recruitment (Section 2.1), geographical coverage and characteristics of experts (Section 2.2), and question methodology (Section 2.3).¹

2.1 Expert Recruitment

We contact economic experts from two main sources. The first group consists of distinguished professionals working at universities, research institutes, central banks, multinational corporations, embassies, and international organizations. Most of these experts were already part of the WES sample and are carefully selected and maintain ties to the ifo Institute or the CESifo network. The second group includes leading academics and researchers in economics identified through the RePEc ranking of authors. Together, these experts represent influential contributors to the academic and public discourse in their respective countries (including Nobel laureates in economics and influential policy advisors).

2.2 Coverage and Expert Characteristics

The EES is designed to ensure broad global coverage of economic experts. In each wave, around 10,000 experts from all regions of the world are invited to participate. The survey achieves a response rate of around 15%, resulting in an average of around 1,500 respondents per wave. The EES consistently collects expert views from more than 120 countries (Figure 1). Participation is particularly strong in the United States, Canada, the United Kingdom, Spain, Germany, Italy, and Austria. The survey also secures solid coverage in South America, Oceania, and parts of Asia. Participation across the African continent is lower than in the Americas, Europe, Asia and Oceania, which partly reflects the smaller pool of contacted experts in Africa due to the limited number of academic institutions.

Table 1 summarizes observable characteristics of respondents in the EES. The majority of the experts are male (84 percent), with female experts accounting for about 14 percent. Respondents are mostly above 45 years old, with the largest age groups between 45–54 years old (29 percent), 55–64 years old (27 percent), and 65 years or older (29 percent), while only a small share (1 percent) are younger than 34 years. Many participants are active in academia (62 percent), while some experts also work in research institutes or think tanks (15 percent), the private sector (10

¹For another overview of the EES, see Gründler et al. (2023b).

Figure 1 Participation in the EES across Countries

Notes: The figure shows the average number of participants per country in the EES over the period Q1 2022 to Q2 2025.

percent), central banks (6 percent), and the public sector (5 percent). Geographically, more than half of the respondents are based in Europe (52 percent), with substantial representation from the Americas (22 percent) and Asia (15 percent), while Africa (8 percent) and Oceania (3 percent) are less strongly represented. Together these demographic and geographic patterns reflect the global academic and policy-oriented scope of the EES.

2.3 Survey Questions

Core Questions To track global political developments, the EES surveys experts on their assessments of both the political situation in their country of expertise and the state of economic policy. Each of these two core dimensions is further divided into specific elements. Regarding the **political situation**, experts evaluate the performance of the government and the political stability in their country. With respect to **economic policy**, they provide both a general assessment and their views on how effectively the government is addressing future challenges. Specifically, the core questions are as follows:

Economic Policy

1. How do you rate your country's current economic policy?
2. How well does your country's economic policy address the challenges of the future?

Table 1 Observable Characteristics of EES Respondents

Category	Subgroup	Share (%)
Gender	Male	84.1
	Female	14.2
Age	<34	1.4
	35–44	16.1
	45–54	28.6
	55–64	27.2
	65+	29.1
Sector/Affiliation	Academia	61.8
	Private Sector	9.5
	Public Sector	5.3
	Central Bank	5.8
	Research Institutes & Think Tanks	14.8
	Other	2.8
Region	Europe	52.4
	Americas	21.7
	Asia	15.2
	Africa	8.2
	Oceania	2.5

Notes: The table shows the shares of experts with individual observable characteristics. The underlying data is from Q2 2025.

Political Situation

1. How do you rate the performance of your country’s current government?
2. How do you rate the stability of your country’s current political situation?

Each of the core questions is measured on a scale from -100 to $+100$.

Implementation The EES runs quarterly and each EES wave runs over a period of two weeks. We contact the experts via email with an invitation to participate in the EES. The experts answer the questions online and can choose the country they wish to provide expertise for. In the survey, the experts are presented with the four core EES questions, as well as changing questions in special modules.

Example: Experts’ Assessments in the United States A suitable example for experts’ assessment of economic policy and the political situation are the United States, illustrated in Figure 2 over the period 2023–2025 (for a more detailed analysis, see Heil et al., 2025a).

Between Q1 2022 and Q4 2024, US experts in the EES consistently rated current economic policy positively, peaking in Q4 2022 with a score of 24 (out of 100). Assessments of policy addressing future challenges were more mixed, with noticeable

Figure 2 Assessment of Economic Policy and Political Situation in the United States

Source: Economic Experts Survey 2022-2025.

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Notes: The figure shows the development of US experts' responses to the core questions over the period Q1 2022 to Q2 2025. The shaded area in Q1 and Q2 2025 marks the waves during Donald Trump's second presidency, while the area shaded in white represents the period of Joe Biden's presidency.

deterioration during the first three quarters of 2023. From Q1 2024 onward, experts judged government performance increasingly critically (-4, -1, -13 in the first three quarters), while since Q2 2023 they also perceived US political stability as markedly worsened (-16 to -28).

A dramatic shift occurred from Q1 2025 onward, when Donald Trump began his second presidential term. At that point, evaluations of both current economic policy and policy for future challenges dropped sharply to -58, government performance fell to -63, and political stability to -52. Experts continued to assign massively negative ratings in Q2 2025, underscoring the strongly critical view of Trump's economic policy among the surveyed economic experts.

Evaluation of Changes We ask experts to evaluate how key variables have changed relative to the previous quarter. This approach enables us to trace the evolution of government performance and political stability over time within individual countries. Focusing on changes rather than absolute levels avoids requiring experts to make cross-country comparisons, which would require a level of informa-

tion unlikely to be uniformly available across respondents.

Open-Ended Text Questions A key feature of the EES is including open-ended text questions alongside the quantitative items. These allow experts to provide qualitative assessments of developments in their country, offering context and justification for their quantitative ratings. Such open-ended responses are now considered state of the art in survey-based research (Haaland et al., 2025), because they provide valuable insights into the reasoning behind expert evaluations and highlight the specific events or dynamics that shape their views.

Special Modules The EES also incorporates special modules that address timely and policy-relevant economic topics. Special modules include, for instance, the global economic impact of the US Inflation Reduction Act (Gründler et al., 2023a) or the expectations of economic experts about their country’s trade policy (Heil et al., 2025b).

Experts as Sources of Information The EES leverages the fact that economic experts possess deep knowledge of their countries’ economic conditions, political institutions, and current developments. By aggregating their assessments, the survey captures a broad spectrum of information sources that are otherwise difficult to obtain through conventional data collection methods.

3 Studies that used the EES or the WES

The results of the EES are regularly published, currently in two forms. The EES reports, which are published every quarter on the website of the ifo Institute, contain a broad overview of the results of the core questions and for (parts of) the special modules.² Since 2025, we also describe results in *EconPol Policy Briefs*, which focus on the views of European experts. One example is the expectations of economic experts about the future of protectionist policies, i.e., the tariff rates on imports (Heil et al., 2025b).

Beyond policy studies, the experts’ assessments and macroeconomic expectations in both the WES and the EES have been used in papers published in economics journals. In Andre et al. (2022) the subjective models of experts about the causes of a range of economic indicators are elicited. Arnemann et al. (2021)

²See <https://www.ifo.de/en/survey/economic-experts-survey> for the reports as well as additional findings of the survey.

examine whether collective memories on the aid and reform programs chosen to handle the 2010 European debt crisis differ between citizens from borrower and lender countries. They disentangle views of experts and non-experts. In the context of the Tax Cuts and Jobs Act, Boumans et al. (2020) use expert assessments of the effects of this large US tax reform on investment activities in other countries. Exploiting the outcome of the US presidential election in November 2020, Boumans et al. (2024) quantify the impact of political leaders on macroeconomic expectations of experts, both in the United States and in other countries around the world. Studying the effect of housing price expectations on spending decisions, Chopra et al. (2025) employ housing price forecasts of experts in the EES to exogenously shift housing price expectations of households in a survey experiment. Blesse et al. (2025) use data from the EES, in a first step, to collect experts' narratives about the increased risk of a recession. These are then, in a second step, offered to households to estimate their willingness to pay for economic narratives. Gründler et al. (2025) provide causal evidence that economic experts serve as effective intermediaries in translating policy signals to the public. Dräger et al. (2025) design a large-scale global survey experiment among EES-experts to study whether peer effects impact expectations about the macroeconomy.

4 Data Access and Usage

The EES data are available as a panel dataset through the LMU-ifo Economics & Business Data Center (EBDC), where also a variable list is provided in English. The dataset is provided in *.dta* (Stata) format (DOI: 10.7805/ebdc-ees-2025) and is updated once a year. Access is possible for researchers with an academic affiliation for non-commercial research purposes and is restricted to on-site use at the EBDC, located at the ifo Institute in Munich. In line with its strict confidentiality policy, the ifo Institute guarantees the secrecy of all survey data: Neither expert names nor institutional affiliations are included in the microdata, ensuring full anonymity of participants. Researchers interested in using the EES microdata for a clearly defined research project should contact the EBDC for details on the access framework and application procedure. The written request has to be approved by the EBDC. Researchers using data from the Economic Experts Survey are kindly requested to cite this paper as a source.

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